

A STRESS GRADIENT APPROACH FOR PREDICTING SIZE EFFECTS ON MODE II DELAMINATION

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ABSTRACT

A nonlocal elastic fracture mechanics approach is here devised for predicting the size effect due to through-thickness compression on mode II delamination. The approach is based on solving the mode II crack-tip stress problem within the framework Eringen's stress gradient elasticity theory. The proposed crack model allows for the presence of cohesive tractions behind the crack tip, despite the underlying theory being linear elastic. The aforementioned approach is applied to describe the increase of fracture toughness with size in "transverse crack tension" coupons.

1 INTRODUCTION

"Transverse crack tension" (TCT) coupons were introduced in the 1990s to measure the mode II interlaminar fracture toughness of fibre-reinforced composites [1-3]. TCT coupons are prismatic and

Fig 1: TCT coupon (not to scale). Delaminations shown in red

homogeneous unidirectional bars, which comprise a block of full-width cut plies at the mid-gauge transverse section, as shown in Fig. 1. The cut plies are arranged symmetrically with respect to the mid through-thickness plane. Upon the application of a remote tensile stress, the stress concentration at the cut location causes four delaminations, which are emanated from the tips of the cut. The delaminations tend to grow symmetrically along the gauge section of the TCT coupon. TCT specimens have also been employed to characterise the mode II fatigue delamination growth rates in glass/ and carbon/epoxy composites [2,4]. TCT coupons have also been referred to as "central cut ply" (CCP) specimens [4].

From elementary linear elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM), it is possible to show [2,4] that the mode II energy release rate (ERR) G_{II} attained at the tips of each of the four delaminations in Fig. 1 is given by [2,4]:

$$G_{II} = \frac{\sigma_\infty^2 t}{4E_{11}} \frac{\chi}{1-\chi}, \quad (1)$$

where σ_∞ is the applied gross-section tensile stress, t and B are respectively the specimen thickness and width, while E_{11} is the longitudinal (fibre-direction) Young's modulus of the composite. In Eq. (1), χ denotes the ratio of the thickness of the cut-ply block to the total specimen thickness; since the material cured ply thickness (CPT) can be assumed constant, χ also represents the ratio of the number of terminated central plies to the total number of plies. Eq. (1) implies that in TCT coupons the ERR is independent from the crack length and from the specimen gauge length. Finite element (FE) simulations [2,3] have shown that G_{II} given in Eq. (1) is attained for delamination lengths in the order of a few times the thickness of the cut-ply block [3]. For shorter delaminations, FE analysis suggests that the actual ERR exceeds the value of G_{II} in Eq. (1); this implies that the onset of interlaminar fracture from the cut-ply block is usually a stable process [2].

Eq. (1) suggests that, for a constant material toughness as assumed in Griffith's fracture criterion, the strength of TCT coupons scales as the inverse square root of the total laminate thickness. However, Wisnom [2] experimentally demonstrated that this is not true. Actually, the strength values obtained for TCT coupons with constant χ imply that the fracture toughness increases with the coupon thickness. For E-glass/913, Wisnom [2] found a 69% increase of G_{II} while scaling up the coupons by a factor of eight. This effect was attributed to two main causes [2-3]: 1) the presence of interlaminar compressive stresses at the delamination tips, due to transverse contraction of the coupon under far-field longitudinal tension; 2) energy dissipation at the interlaminar crack tip due to plastic deformation, which is not accounted for in LEFM. Regarding the second cause, the influence of plasticity on the actual strength becomes stronger as the specimen gets thinner, because larger stresses have to be applied in order to cause failure. Bazant et al. [5] demonstrated that the strength of TCT coupons could be represented by the following equation:

$$\sigma_{\infty} = \frac{\sigma_u}{\sqrt{1 + \alpha n}}, \quad (2)$$

where α is a constant, n is the number of cut plies and σ_u is the limit strength for $n \rightarrow 0$. Bazant et al. [5] identified both σ_u and α in Eq. (2) from Wisnom's data [2], thus Eq. (2) cannot be considered a "predictive" model, but rather a "fitting" tool. Actually, for $n \rightarrow 0$, Eq. (2) must give the strength of an un-notched tensile coupon, i.e. σ_u must be equal to the longitudinal tensile strength of the composite. In [5] the estimated value of σ_u was 1412 MPa, which is in excellent agreement with the 1400 MPa longitudinal tensile strength declared by the manufacturer for E-glass/913.

Van der Meer and Sluys [6] carried out a comprehensive progressive FE failure analysis of TCT coupons. They employed a cohesive law that accounts for the frictional behaviour of dis-bonded interfaces and also considered the non-linear shear response of composite plies. The results in [6] show how the size effect in TCT coupons is due to a complex interplay between friction and plasticity. In particular, the FE models highlighted the presence of highly localized and high shear strain regions neighbouring the dis-bonding interface. This required the adoption of extremely fine meshes, with characteristic element sizes in the order of microns. In [6] it was recognised that, albeit the FE analysis reproduced the correct trend of size effect for TCT specimens, the associated computational cost was too high to cope with problems involving multiple delaminations. Moreover, the simulation results were highly sensitive to the actual value of the interface friction coefficient, which is very difficult if not impossible to measure experimentally.

2 NONLOCAL ELASTIC FRACTURE MECHANICS (NL-LEFM)

2.1 Non-local "stress gradient" theory

Eringen [7] introduced the nonlocal elasticity theory in the 1970s. The fundamental concept underpinning nonlocal elasticity is that there exist finite-range forces within elastic bodies. Hence the stress-strain response cannot be described in a point-wise fashion; material elements belonging to nonlocal continua have elastic influence domains with finite size. Nonlocal elasticity was initially devised as a bridge between crystal lattice dynamics and continuum theory and, nowadays, it is widely employed to describe the behaviour of nano-scale structural assemblies. The constitutive equations of linear small-strain nonlocal elasticity can be stated in the following differential form:

$$\sigma_{ij} - \ell^2 \nabla^2 \sigma_{ij} = C_{ijkl} \varepsilon_{kl}, \quad (1)$$

where σ_{ij} is the nonlocal stress, while ε_{ij} is the classical engineering strain. C_{ijkl} is the 4-th order tensor comprising the coefficients of the classical Hookean three-dimensional constitutive equations.

From a physical point of view, Eq. (3) implies that a diffusion process of classical Hookean tractions governs the nonlocal stress, with ℓ representing a characteristic length scale over which the aforementioned diffusion takes place. In other words, ℓ is dependent on the finite range of "cohesive" elastic forces that arise within a nonlocal continuum. Similarly, one can state that ℓ is related to the

size of the elastic influence domain of a nonlocal material particle. At the nano-scale, ℓ can be identified by matching wave dispersion curves using discrete atomic and equivalent continuum models [8]. The application of nonlocal stress-gradient elasticity to crack problems in isotropic and orthotropic materials yielded the following fundamental results: 1) the stress at the crack tip is finite [9-10]; 2) the maximum stress is attained at a finite distance ahead of the geometrical crack tip [9-10]; 3) the crack tip displacement field in nonlocal elasticity is the same as its classical counterpart [9]; 4) there exists a cohesive region behind the crack tip whereby self balanced tractions act on the crack surfaces [11].

2.2 Crack-tip nonlocal stress field

The size of this cohesive region depends on ℓ and on the stiffness, strength and fracture properties of the material. Since crack-tip stresses are finite, fracture can be described using only stress-based criteria. For a mixed-mode I/II crack in an orthotropic material, it has been demonstrated that the nonlocal crack-tip stress field that obeys the constitutive equations (1) is given by [11]:

$$\sigma_{ij}(r, \theta) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi\ell}} \sum_{m=I}^{II} K_m H_{ij}^{(m)} \left(\frac{r}{\ell}, \theta; \lambda, \rho \right), \quad (2)$$

where

$$H_{ij}^{(m)} \left(\frac{r}{\ell}, \theta; \lambda, \rho \right) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{2}} \int_0^\infty \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{-\pi+\varepsilon}^{\pi-\varepsilon} K_0 \left(\frac{|r-r'|}{\ell} \right) g_{ij}^{(m)}(\theta'; \lambda, \rho) \sqrt{\frac{r'}{\ell}} d \left(\frac{r'}{\ell} \right) d\theta'. \quad (3)$$

Eqs. (2)-(3) represent a convolution of the classical (i.e. nonlocal) stresses via the modified Bessel function of the second kind and order zero K_0 [11]. In Eqs. (2-3) (r, θ) and (r', θ') are coincident polar coordinate systems with origin at the crack tip, as shown in Fig. 2. The functions $g_{ij}^{(m)}(\theta'; \lambda, \rho)$ express the angular dependency of the classical stress field, as detailed in [11-12]. Finally, λ and ρ are the normalized stiffness coefficients, which for an orthotropic material are given by [13]:

$$\lambda = \frac{E_2}{E_1}, \quad \rho = \frac{\sqrt{E_1 E_2}}{2G_{12}} - \sqrt{\nu_{12} \nu_{21}}, \quad (4)$$

Since here the emphasis is on delamination problems for uni-directional composites, in Eq. (4) E_1 and E_2 represent the Young's moduli in the fibre and through-thickness directions, respectively; G_{12} is the through-thickness shear modulus. Finally ν_{12} and ν_{21} are the Poisson's ratios, which in an orthotropic material are related by the identity $E_1 \nu_{21} = E_2 \nu_{12}$. Eqs. (4) are strictly valid for plane stress problems; however, if a plane strain regime prevails, equivalent moduli can be readily identified using modified compliance coefficients, as discussed in [13].

Focusing on a mode II problem, from Eq. (2), the relation between the ERR at the crack tip and the stress intensity factor in LEFM (classical elasticity) is given by [13]:

$$G_{II} = \alpha_{II} K_{II}^2, \quad (5)$$

where:

$$\alpha_{II} = \sqrt[4]{\lambda} \sqrt{\frac{1+\rho}{2E_1 E_2}}. \quad (6)$$

Taking advantage of Eqs. (3) and (5), the mode II nonlocal stress field (NL-LEFM) on the crack line ahead ($\theta = 0$) of the crack tip can be expressed as [11]:

$$\sigma_{12}(r, 0) = \sqrt{\frac{G_{II}}{\pi\alpha_{II}\ell}} \Psi_{12}^{(II)} \left(\frac{r}{\ell}; \lambda, \rho \right), \quad (7)$$

where:

$$\Psi_{12}^{(II)}\left(\frac{r}{\ell}; \lambda, \rho\right) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{2}} \int_0^{\infty} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{-\pi+\varepsilon}^{\pi-\varepsilon} K_0\left(\sqrt{\xi^2 + \xi'^2 - 2\xi\xi' \cos\theta'}\right) g_{12}^{(II)}(\theta'; \lambda, \rho) \sqrt{\xi'} d\xi' d\theta', \quad (8)$$

with $\xi = r/\ell$, $\xi' = r'/\ell$.

From Eqs. (7-8), at the crack tip, the stress is given by:

$$\sigma_{12}(0,0) = \sqrt{\frac{G_{II}}{\pi\alpha_{II}\ell}} \Psi_{12}^{(II)}(0; \lambda, \rho) \cong 6.74 \times 10^{-2} G_{12}^{(II)}(\lambda, \rho) \sqrt{\frac{G_{II}}{\alpha_{II}\ell}} \quad (9)$$

where:

$$G_{12}^{(II)}(\lambda, \rho) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{-\pi+\varepsilon}^{\pi-\varepsilon} g_{12}^{(II)}(\theta'; \lambda, \rho) d\theta' < \infty. \quad (10)$$

Since $G_{12}^{(II)}(\lambda, \rho)$ in Eq. (10) is a finite quantity [11], the nonlocal crack-tip stress in Eq. (9) is also finite. All the other components of both the classical and nonlocal stress tensors are zero for a mode II crack. Similarly, *behind* the crack tip ($\theta = \pm\pi$) one finds [11]:

$$\sigma_{12}(r, \pm\pi) = \sqrt{\frac{G_{II}}{\pi\alpha_{II}\ell}} \Upsilon_{12}^{(II)}\left(\frac{r}{\ell}; \lambda, \rho\right), \quad (11)$$

with:

$$\Upsilon_{12}^{(II)}\left(\frac{r}{\ell}; \lambda, \rho\right) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{2}} \int_0^{\infty} \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{-\pi+\varepsilon}^{\pi-\varepsilon} K_0\left(\sqrt{\xi^2 + \xi'^2 + 2\xi\xi' \cos\theta'}\right) g_{12}^{(II)}(\theta'; \lambda, \rho) \sqrt{\xi'} d\xi' d\theta'. \quad (12)$$

again with $\xi = r/\ell$, $\xi' = r'/\ell$.

Note that by virtue of Eqs. (8) and (10) one has $\Psi_{12}^{(II)}(0; \lambda, \rho) = \Upsilon_{12}^{(II)}(0; \lambda, \rho)$, hence the nonlocal stress is finite valued and continuous at the crack-tip.

A plot of the mode II stress field in the neighbourhood of the crack tip is presented in Fig. 3, for various combinations of λ and ρ . The peak shear stress is reached ahead of the crack tip, at a location that depends both on ℓ and on the elastic properties of the orthotropic material. In Fig. 3, one can also observe the presence of a cohesive zone behind the crack tip (i.e. $r/\ell < 0$), where the stress is given by Eq. (11) and it decays asymptotically to zero as the distance from the fracture vertex increases. The extent of such cohesive region is again a function of ℓ , λ and ρ .

Fig. 2: Crack-tip reference frame

Fig. 3: Mode II crack-tip stress

2.3 Energy release rate (ERR) in nonlocal elasticity

Since the displacement field at the crack tip is the same for classical and nonlocal elasticity [7-11], the mode II sliding behind the crack tip can be written as [12]:

$$u(r, \pi) = -u(r, -\pi) = 2\sqrt{\frac{2\alpha_{II}G_{II}}{\pi}}x, \quad (13)$$

where x is an abscissa than spans the negative x_I semi-axis in Fig. 2.

In NL-LEFM, due to the anti-symmetry of the shear stress (11) with respect to the crack plane, the work done to separate the crack faces per unit area is given by

$$w_d = 2 \int_0^\infty \sigma_{12} [u(r, \pi)] du(r, \pi). \quad (14)$$

For NL-LEFM the following theorem holds:

Theorem: The mode II de-cohesion work in non-local elasticity (14) is equivalent to the classical crack-tip energy release rate, i.e. $w_d = G_{II}$.

Proof: Substituting Eqs. (2-3) into Eq. (14), the mode II de-cohesion work can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} w_d &= 2\sqrt{\frac{G_{II}}{2\pi\alpha_{II}}} \int_0^\infty \lim_{\theta \rightarrow \pi} \left[\int_0^\infty \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_{-\pi+\varepsilon}^{\pi-\varepsilon} \frac{1}{2\pi\ell^2} K_0 \left(\frac{|\underline{r}-\underline{r}'|}{\ell} \right) g_{12}^{(II)}(\theta'; \lambda, \rho) \frac{1}{\sqrt{r'}} r' dr' d\theta' \right] du(r, \pi) = \\ &= 2 \int_0^\infty \lim_{\theta \rightarrow \pi} \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^2-\Sigma} \frac{1}{2\pi\ell^2} K_0 \left(\frac{|\underline{r}-\underline{r}'|}{\ell} \right) \bar{\sigma}_{12}(\underline{r}') d\underline{r}' \right] du(r, \pi), \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where

$$\bar{\sigma}_{12}(\underline{r}') = \bar{\sigma}_{12}(r', \theta') = \sqrt{\frac{G_{II}}{2\pi\alpha_{II}r'}} g_{12}^{(II)}(\theta'; \lambda, \rho). \quad (16)$$

Eq. (16) represents the classical (LEFM) asymptotic stress field [12]. Note that since the convolution in the square brackets in the last member of (15) is commutative, one has:

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2-\Sigma} \frac{1}{2\pi\ell^2} K_0 \left(\frac{|\underline{r}-\underline{r}'|}{\ell} \right) \bar{\sigma}_{12}(\underline{r}') d\underline{r}' = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2-\Sigma} \frac{1}{2\pi\ell^2} K_0 \left(\frac{|\underline{r}'|}{\ell} \right) \bar{\sigma}_{12}(\underline{r}-\underline{r}') d\underline{r}'. \quad (17)$$

Substituting Eq. (17) into Eq. (15) and permuting the integrals one finds:

$$w_d = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2-\Sigma} \frac{1}{2\pi\ell^2} K_0 \left(\frac{|\underline{r}'|}{\ell} \right) \left[2 \int_0^\infty \lim_{\theta \rightarrow \pi} \bar{\sigma}_{12}(\underline{r}-\underline{r}') du(r, \pi) \right] d\underline{r}'. \quad (18)$$

In the limit $\theta \rightarrow \pi$, the vector $\underline{r}-\underline{r}'$ identifies a geometric point that belongs to the “upper” crack surface. As shown in Fig. 4, this point is located at a distance x behind the crack tip, being $x = \lim_{\theta \rightarrow \pi} |\underline{r}|$.

From Eq. (13) one has:

$$du(r, \pi) = du(x) = \frac{u(x)}{2x} dx. \quad (19)$$

Substituting Eq. (19) into the integral within square brackets in Eq. (18) and taking advantage of the second mean value theorem for improper integrals lead to:

$$2 \int_0^\infty \lim_{\theta \rightarrow \pi} \bar{\sigma}_{12}(\underline{r}-\underline{r}') du(r, \pi) = \int_0^\infty \bar{\sigma}_{12}(x) \frac{u(x)}{x} dx = \lim_{\Delta \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\Delta} \int_0^\Delta \bar{\sigma}_{12}(\Delta-x) u(x) dx. \quad (20)$$

The well-known Irwin’s crack-closure integral appears in the last member of the identities (20). This integral gives the classical energy release rate at the crack tip G_{II} . Substituting Eq. (20) into Eq. (15)

yields:

$$w_d = G_{II} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2 - \Sigma} \frac{1}{2\pi\ell^2} K_0\left(\frac{|r'|}{\ell}\right) dr'. \quad (21)$$

Note that the modified Bessel function of the second kind satisfies the identity:

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^2 - \Sigma} \frac{1}{2\pi\ell^2} K_0\left(\frac{|r'|}{\ell}\right) dr' = 1. \quad (22)$$

Substituting Eq. (22) into Eq. (21) completes the proof of the theorem.

An alternative compact expression of the de-cohesion work is provided by:

$$w_d = G_{II} \frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \frac{\Upsilon_{12}^{(II)}(\xi; \lambda, \rho)}{\sqrt{\xi}} d\xi, \quad (23)$$

where once again $\xi = r / \ell$.

Fig. 4: Arrangement of vectors in Eq. (18).

2.4 Fracture Criterion

Since the do-cohesion work per unit area in nonlocal elasticity is equal to the ERR in LEFM, fracture in NL-LEFM is also described by the Griffith's criterion, i.e. a crack will propagate when the ERR reaches a critical value G_{IIc} that corresponds to the material fracture toughness.

However, since the crack-tip stress is finite in NL-LEFM, the Griffith's energy-based fracture criterion can be equivalently formulated in terms of stress. In mathematical terms, the Griffith's criterion postulates that fracture occurs when:

$$G_{II} = G_{IIc}. \quad (24)$$

As shown in Fig. 3., the peak shear stress is reached at a finite distance \hat{x} ahead of the crack tip, which depends only on the material normalised stiffness coefficients λ and ρ . By virtue of Eqs. (7) and (24), the peak value of the shear stress at fracture is given by

$$\hat{\sigma}_{12} = \sqrt{\frac{G_{IIc}}{\pi\alpha_{II}\ell}} \hat{\Psi}_{12}^{(II)}(\lambda, \rho), \quad (25)$$

where $\hat{\Psi}_{12}^{(II)}(\lambda, \rho) = \Psi_{12}^{(II)}(\hat{x}/\ell; \lambda, \rho)$. However, the peak shear stress in Eq. (25) must be equal to the material shear strength τ_c . Hence, setting $\hat{\sigma}_{12} = \tau_c$ and solving with respect to ℓ leads to the following expression of the nonlocal length scale:

$$\ell = \frac{G_{IIc}}{\pi\alpha_{II}\tau_c^2} \left[\hat{\Psi}_{12}^{(II)}(\lambda, \rho) \right]^2. \quad (26)$$

Eq. (26) allows identifying the nonlocal length scale as a characteristic material property that depends on both toughness and strength. By virtue of Eq. (26), the crack-line shear stress field from Eq. (7) can be equivalently expressed as:

$$\sigma_{12}(r, 0) = \frac{\tau_c}{\hat{\Psi}_{12}^{(II)}(\lambda, \rho)} \sqrt{\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}}} \Psi_{12}^{(II)}\left(\frac{r}{\ell}; \lambda, \rho\right). \quad (27)$$

Eq. (27) proves that, at least in mode II, nonlocal elasticity allows unifying strength and energy-based

fracture criteria, since the failure stress of the material can be reached if and only if $G_{II} = G_{IIc}$.

2.5 Physical considerations

Albeit originally devised to describe the behaviour of nano-scale continua, it is here advocated that nonlocal elasticity can be employed to model the interlaminar fracture of composites. In other words, it is here assumed that stress-gradient elasticity is also valid at the micro/meso-scales for fibre-reinforced plastics, at least when mode II fracture is of concern. The rationale for this assumption is

Fig. 5: Nominal (a) and actual (b) [14] configurations of a mode II delamination close to the crack tip.

explained by observing the actual morphology of a mode II delamination in a composite material in Fig. 5.b) [14], in comparison with the nominal configuration assumed in LEFM, shown in Fig. 5.a). Mode II delaminations grow via the progressive onset of inter-ply cracks oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ with respect to the crack propagation direction [14]. The orientation angle identifies the direction of the tensile principal stress. Once the inter-ply micro-cracks have initiated, they grow as voids separated by matrix bridges, which experience extensive plastic deformation, as demonstrated in Fig. 5.b). The final failure of the resin bridges

leads to the formation of shear hackles [14]. Therefore, the growth of mode II delaminations is entirely governed by the development and self-similar propagation of a bridging zone behind the crack tip. Considering two points (P and Q in Fig. 5) on the nominal crack surfaces, the associated tractions will be influenced by the stress redistribution over the entire bridging region. Hence, non-locality effects arise because of the presence of alternative load paths, provided by the matrix bridges. In LEFM, the tractions on the crack surfaces are zero, unless the crack edges are directly loaded. It is evident that for unloaded cracks, LEFM can be applied only if the size of the bridging region is small compared with the crack length. On the other hand, nonlocal elasticity, i.e. NL-LEFM, provides a framework for describing the behaviour of bridged cracks, due to the presence of a cohesive region in the wake of the delamination tip, as highlighted in Fig. 3. Cohesive zone modelling has also been extensively applied to describe the progressive failure of bridged interfaces in composite materials [15]. In cohesive models, fracture mechanics is induced “a posteriori” by imposing that the area under the traction-displacement curve equals the material fracture toughness. This property is satisfied “a priori” by NL-LEFM. Moreover, while cohesive zone models are intrinsically nonlinear, nonlocal elasticity provides a linear framework for describing the behaviour of bridged delamination.

As mentioned before, NL-LEFM predicts that the peak stress is attained at a finite distance ahead of the crack tip. From a qualitative point of view, this is in line with what can be inferred Fig. 5.b). The crack tip can be located at the centre of the last void to the left, since the delamination is growing from the right to the left. Since the propagation is self-similar, a further crack/void will appear further to the left, letting the crack tip jump by a finite distance. This distance is a fraction of the nonlocal length scale, usually in the order of $0.3 \div 0.8 \ell$ [11], and it can be calculated from the material strength, toughness and the normalised stiffness coefficients.

3 MODE II SIZE EFFECT

3.1 Effect of through-thickness compression

The presence of through-thickness stresses influences both the shear strength and the mode II fracture toughness [16]. For moderate levels of through-thickness compression σ_2 , it has been demonstrated [16] that the interlaminar shear strength of a fibre-reinforced composite can be expressed as:

$$\tau_c = \tau_c^0 \left(1 - \eta \frac{\sigma_2}{\tau_c^0} \right), \quad (28)$$

where τ_c^0 is the shear strength corresponding to $\sigma_2 = 0$ and η is a material-dependent coefficient. Since the nonlocal length scale ℓ is an intrinsic material property, it can still be calculated by Eq. (26), provided that the strength and toughness values employed are those for zero interlaminar compression. Let the critical ERR for $\sigma_2 = 0$ be denoted as G_{IIc}^0 . Then Eq. (26) is rewritten as:

$$\ell = \frac{G_{IIc}^0}{\pi \alpha_{II} (\tau_c^0)^2} \left[\hat{\Psi}_{12}^{(II)}(\lambda, \rho) \right]^2, \quad (29)$$

which provides the aforementioned expression of the intrinsic, i.e. compression independent, nonlocal length scale. Considering Eq. (25) and setting the peak shear stress to the corrected strength from Eq. (28) leads to

$$\tau_c^0 \left(1 - \eta \frac{\sigma_2}{\tau_c^0} \right) = \sqrt{\frac{G_{IIc}}{\pi \alpha_{II} \ell}} \hat{\Psi}_{12}^{(II)}(\lambda, \rho). \quad (30)$$

Substituting the expression of the nonlocal length scale from eq. (29) into eq. (30) and solving with respect to G_{IIc} yields the following expression of the fracture toughness in presence of through-thickness compressive stresses:

$$G_{IIc} = G_{IIc}^0 \left(1 - \eta \frac{\sigma_2}{\tau_c^0} \right)^2. \quad (31)$$

Eq. (31) is the same expression that has been proposed in [15] in order to account for the toughness enhancement due to through-thickness compression. However, here Eq. (31) has been obtained directly from considerations drawn from nonlocal elasticity, while in [16] it was empirically introduced to fit experimental data via finite element analysis.

3.2 Through-thickness compression in TCT coupons

Eqs. (30-31) are strictly valid for a uniform through-thickness compressive stress. Another problem that arises is also how to experimentally determine the fracture toughness value at zero through-thickness compression G_{IIc}^0 .

The stiffness properties of unidirectional E-glass/913 are given in Tab. 1. By means of Eqs. (4) and (6), these values yield:

$$\lambda = 0.3508, \quad \rho = 2.8178, \quad \alpha_{II} = 4.895 \times 10^{-5} \text{ MPa}^{-1}. \quad (32)$$

Wisnom [2] considered two sets of E-glass/913 TCT coupons; for the first set he chose $\chi = 1/5$ and thicknesses of 0.635 mm (5 plies), 1.27 mm (10 plies), 2.54 mm (20 plies) and 5.08 mm (40 plies). For the second set comprised specimens with $\chi = 1/9$ and thicknesses of 1.27 mm (10 plies) and 2.54 mm (20 plies). All the coupons were tested under static tension. Wisnom [2] observed a delamination “initiation” stage, which consisted of a slow propagation of interlaminar cracks from the cut location, up to a length of 2 mm on each side. Afterwards, delaminations quickly grew reaching the end tabs and this propagation stage took place together with a sharp load reduction. The peak load before the drop associated to the fast delamination growth was considered for estimating the propagation G_{IIc} from Eq. (1).

All the tests considered in [2] are here modelled via finite element (FE) analysis, using the commercial software MSC/NASTRAN; 8-noded quadratic isoparametric elements are employed. A plane stress regime is assumed. The material is assumed to be linear elastic and orthotropic, having the stiffness properties already presented in Tab. 1. Only a quarter of the actual coupon geometry has been meshed,

with symmetry boundary conditions on the mid through-thickness plane and at half the gauge section. A fine mesh has been introduced from the model edge comprising the cut plies up to a length of 12mm; this mesh consists of square elements with edge length of 0.0635 mm through the full thickness. This value of the edge length was determined from convergence studies on the crack-tip ERR obtained via VCCT, as well as on the distribution of the through-thickness normal stress in the neighbourhood of the delamination vertex. For distances above 12 mm from the cut-ply end, the mesh has been progressively coarsened in order to allow a smooth introduction of the applied tensile loading, while reducing the overall computational cost.

Engineering constant		Value
E_1	[GPa]	43.9
E_2	[GPa]	15.4
n_{12}	–	0.3
G_{12}	[GPa]	4.34

Table 1: Lamina stiffness properties for E-glass/913 [17].

In the models, the element edges lying on the delamination path have been disconnected, thus creating a set of coincident nodes. These have been reconnected via DOF springs elements, with peel and shear stiffness of 10^6 N/mm. In order to propagate the interlaminar cracks, the spring elements are deleted and substituted with frictionless gap elements, having compressive stiffness of 10^6 N/mm. The aforementioned stiffness values for the spring and gap elements have been determined via a convergence study on both the classical crack-tip ERR and the distribution of through-thickness normal stress along the crack faces. The initial delamination length was set to 2 mm, which is the experimental value corresponding to the onset of propagation [2].

The FE models were run for crack lengths ranging from 2 mm to 12 mm, with increments of 1 mm. The distribution of through-thickness compressive stress along the delamination propagation path was found to be the same for whole crack length range mentioned above. However, the values of the compressive stresses were strongly dependent on the thickness of the specimen and on χ . The results of the FE simulations are summarized in Fig. 6. First of all, for all the coupon configurations, it was found that the gap elements behind the crack tip were closed at a level of far-field tension in the order of 40 MPa, which is at least one order of magnitude less than the experimental failure loads. Hence, the through-thickness direct stress σ_2 can be considered as linear functions of the applied far-field stress σ_∞ . This is the reason why the results in Fig. 6 are normalised with respect to the applied far-field tension.

Fig. 6 shows that the maximum through-thickness compression is attained at the crack tip location. The magnitude of the compressive stresses increases with the specimen thickness at constant χ . Compressive stresses also become larger when increasing the number of cut plies at constant thickness. Moving away from the delamination tip, the magnitude of the compressive stresses decreases. Actually, for the thinner specimens, the through-thickness stress becomes tensile at a sufficient distance ahead of the crack tip.

3.3 Size effect in TCT coupons

Considering the results of the FE analysis discussed in the previous section, it is possible to express the interlaminar normal stress in the neighbourhood of the delamination tip as a linear function of the applied gross-section stress, i.e.

$$\sigma_2 = f_2(x, t, \chi) \sigma_\infty, \quad (33)$$

where x is the distance from the crack tip. The function $f_2(x, t, \chi)$ is that plotted in Fig. 6. Fig. 7 shows the crack-tip nonlocal shear stress distribution for the material data given in Tab. 1; the location of the peak shear stress is at $\hat{x} = 0.8167\ell$, with $\hat{\Psi}_{12}^{(II)} = 0.3478$.

Fig. 6: Predicted through-thickness direct stress versus distance from the interlaminar crack tip for the various coupon configurations tested in [2].

Fig. 7: Non-local shear stress distribution for a mode II crack in E-glass/913;
 (a) comparison with LEFM; (b) zoomed view with peak stress point -
 $\hat{x} = 0.8167\ell$, $\hat{\Psi}_{12}^{(II)} = 0.3478$

In order to estimate the nonlocal length scale from Eq. (29), it is necessary to provide values for both the interlaminar shear stress and the mode II fracture toughness at zero interlaminar compression. Cui and Wisnom [18] carried out a comprehensive FE and experimental study of the stress distribution on three- and four-point bending short beam shear coupons and suggested a reference shear strength value of 75 MPa for E-glass/913, as reported in Tab. 2. The mode II fracture toughness value given in Tab. 2 was obtained employing end loaded split cantilever coupons, which are not affected spurious interlaminar compressive stresses.

Engineering constant		Value	Ref.
τ_c^0	[MPa]	75	[18]
G_{IIc}^0	[kJ/m ²]	1.06	[19]
σ_{2c}	[MPa]	96	[16]
η	-	0.74	[16]

Table 2: Interlaminar strength and toughness properties for E-glass/913.

Thus, from the data in Tab. 1-2, the nonlocal length scale for mode II fracture in E-glass/913 is found to be

$$\ell = 0.1774 \text{ mm.} \quad (34)$$

Hence, from Fig. 7.b, the location of the peak shear stress point is at:

$$\hat{x} = 0.1449 \text{ mm.} \quad (35)$$

Substituting Eq. (1) into Eq. (7) and evaluating the results at the peak shear stress location yields:

$$\hat{\sigma}_{12} = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{\infty} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\pi \alpha_{II} E_{11}} \frac{t}{\ell} \frac{\chi}{1-\chi}} \hat{\Psi}_{12}^{(II)}(\lambda, \rho). \quad (36)$$

Introducing Eq. (28) and (33) into Eq. (36) leads to:

$$\tau_c^0 \left[1 - \eta \frac{\hat{f}_2(t, \chi)}{\tau_c^0} \sigma_{\infty} \right] = \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{\infty} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\pi \alpha_{II} E_{11}} \frac{t}{\ell} \frac{\chi}{1-\chi}} \hat{\Psi}_{12}^{(II)}(\lambda, \rho). \quad (37)$$

where $\hat{f}_2(t, \chi) = f_2(\hat{x}, t, \chi)$. The actual value is obtained from the FE results performing a linear interpolation of the data in Fig. 6. Solving Eq. (37) with respect to the applied far field stress gives:

$$\sigma_{\infty} = \frac{2\tau_c^0 \sqrt{\pi \alpha_{II} E_{11} \ell (1-\chi)}}{\hat{\Psi}_{12}^{(II)}(\lambda, \rho) \sqrt{t\chi} + 2\eta \hat{f}_2(t, \chi) \sqrt{\pi \alpha_{II} E_{11} \ell (1-\chi)}}, \quad \hat{f}_2(t, \chi) \leq 0 \quad (38)$$

Eq. (38) provides the expression of the applied tensile stress that causes mode II delamination propagation according to NL-LEFM and accounting for the presence of compressive interlaminar stresses ahead of the crack tip.

At the peak stress location given in Eq. (35), Fig. 6 actually shows that the direct interlaminar stress is positive for the 0.635 mm thick specimens with $\chi = 1/4$ and for the 1.270 mm thick coupons for $\chi = 1/9$. Therefore, in these two cases, a quadratic stress interaction criterion [16] is appropriate for describing interlaminar failure. By means of the notation introduced above, the quadratic criterion reads:

$$\left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{12}}{\tau_c^0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\hat{f}_2}{\sigma_{2c}} \right)^2 \sigma_{\infty}^2 = 1, \quad (39)$$

where σ_{2c} is the interlaminar tensile strength, which is given in Tab. 2 for E-glass/913.

Introducing Eq. (36) into Eq. (39) and solving with respect to the applied tensile stress leads to the fracture criterion in presence of interlaminar tension:

$$\sigma_{\infty} = \frac{2\tau_c^0 \sigma_{3c} \sqrt{\pi \alpha_{II} E_{11} \ell (1 - \chi)}}{\sqrt{t \chi \sigma_{3c}^2 \left[\hat{\Psi}_{12}^{(II)}(\lambda, \rho) \right]^2 + 4 \hat{f}_2^2 \left[\tau_c^0 \right]^2 \pi \alpha_{II} E_{11} \ell (1 - \chi)}} \quad (40)$$

Fig. 8 presents the results obtained using Eq. (38) and (40) and provides a comparison with the experimental data from [2] and the FE simulations based on frictional cohesive elements with matrix plasticity in [6]. The red continuous line gives the fracture stress that would be obtained employing LEFM considering the toughness value for the thinnest coupons as a reference; the LEFM scaling is proportional to the inverse square root of the specimen thickness. Fig. 8 demonstrates that LEFM is not able to capture the size effect in TCT coupons. The FE simulations are generally in good agreement with the experimental data, with the obvious exception of the 2.54 mm thick coupons with $\chi = 1/9$. However, as pointed out in the introduction, the results from [6] were obtained using meshes with characteristic element sizes in the order of a few microns; the presence of damage and plasticity made these FE models extremely onerous to run.

The NL-LEFM approach proposed in this paper provides results that are comparable with those of a very detailed FE analysis, but at a fraction of the computational cost. However the strength of the 0.635 mm coupons is over-predicted and the reasons for this discrepancy deserves to be further investigated.

Generally speaking, the thinner the specimen, the more pronounced the effect of plasticity will tend to be; this is a consequence of the increasing value of the gross section stress needed to fracture the coupon. A relatively large plastic area compared with the through-thickness dimension of the specimen will tend to invalidate the small scale yielding assumption on which LEFM, and consequently NL-LEFM, are based. Hence, one may expect that the fracture stress values for the thinner specimens would be better captured by elasto-plastic FE analyses as those in [6].

Regarding the case of coupons with thickness of 2.540 mm and $\chi = 1/9$, also the NL-LEFM approach proposed here gives results in agreement with the FE analysis in [6], but both are far off the actual experimental value. The reasons for such discrepancy are unclear. In a NL-LFEM perspective, the only possible justification is that the through-thickness compressive stresses for the 2.540 mm and $\chi = 1/9$ case are significantly underestimated in the FE models, but again there is no explanation as why this could have happened.

Fig. 8: Experimental data and numerical predictions of size effect in TCT coupons.

9 CONCLUSIONS

The principles of nonlocal linear elastic fracture mechanics (NL-LEFM) have been recalled. It has been demonstrated that NL-LEFM allows linking Griffith's energy-based fracture criterion with a "strength of material" approach. Albeit these results have been demonstrated valid only for mode II fracture, the extension to a mode I regime is straightforward. The analysis of mixed-mode fracture by a NL-LEFM is more challenging and currently under investigation.

NL-LEFM appears particularly suitable for describing the progressive delamination of composite materials, since it naturally allows for the presence of a cohesive region behind the crack tip. One of the most interesting aspects of NL-LEFM is that cohesive stresses exist within the framework of a continuum theory that is still linear elastic. It is well known that cohesive stresses play a significant role in the propagation of interlaminar cracks in composites, which is influenced by "bridging" phenomena acting simultaneously on several scales, from nanoscopic polymer crazing to mesoscopic fibre bridging.

A NL-LEFM approach has been devised for the analysis of transverse crack tension coupons (TCT). The size effect on the strength of TCT specimens has been explained by considering the through-thickness compressive stresses that locally enhance the material strength. The results presented are in good agreement with experimental data and with computationally expensive FE simulations based on frictional cohesive zone models coupled with bulk elasto-plastic behaviour.

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